

Construction of a novel polymeric membrane ion selective sensor based on 3-hydroxy-*N'*-(pyridine-2-ylmethylene)-2-naphthohydrazide to determination of Er³⁺

Hassan Ali Zamani*^a, Fatemeh Joz-Yarmohammadi^a and Mohammad Reza Abedi^b

^aDepartment of Applied Chemistry, Mashhad Branch, Islamic Azad University, Mashhad, Iran

E-mail : haszamani@yahoo.com

^bDepartment of Applied Chemistry, Quchan Branch, Islamic Azad University, Quchan, Iran

Manuscript received online 12 September 2015, accepted 02 March 2016

Abstract : A newly designed ion selective electrode based on PVC membrane was fabricated by 3-hydroxy-*N'*-(pyridine-2-ylmethylene)-2-naphthohydrazide as a neutral carrier, sodium tetraphenylborate as an ionic additive and acetophenone as a plasticizer to measurement the difference of potential caused by variations in the concentration of erbium ions. Regarding to the obtained results, the best efficiency of this electrode was get by composition (w/w) of the membrane contained 67% AP, 30% PVC, 1% NaTPB and 2% ionophore. This erbium electrode was illustrated Nernstian behavior with calibration slope equal 21.3 ± 0.6 mV per decade, and a vast working concentration range of 1.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-2} M with lower limit of detection 7.0×10^{-7} M over a pH range of 3.1–9.7. The response time of electrode was about 10 s. The selectivity of sensor for Er³⁺ ion was assessed in present of other interfering cations by matched potential method. According to given results the electrode has an acceptable sensitivity toward Er³⁺ ion in comparison with other metal ions. In case of analytical application such as potentiometric titration this erbium electrode could be applied successfully as an indicator electrode.

Keywords : Potentiometric method, ion selective electrode, PVC membrane, 3-hydroxy-*N'*-(pyridine-2-ylmethylene)-2-naphthohydrazide.

Introduction

Among the numerous techniques in order to measuring ions *in vivo* or *in vitro*, the direct potentiometric method via ion selective electrodes based on PVC membrane due to variety advantages such as cost effective, ease of supplying and usage, ease of displacement, make quick work, relatively high selectivity, widish working range, usability in turbid samples and so many else, in comparison with other analytical methods, which are time consuming, involving multiple sample utilization and too expensive for most analytical laboratories such as spectrophotometry, mass spectrometry (MS), inductively couple plasma atomic emission spectrometry (ICP-AES), inductively couple plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS), X-ray fluorescence spectrometry, etc., is one of the most widely used methods between researchers¹⁻⁷. The statistics show just a few numbers of sensors for Er^{III} ion among the

recently reported PVC membrane electrodes⁸⁻³⁵.

Erbium is a soft silvery metal with malleable and glossy properties. It is the twelfth element in the lanthanide series with atomic number 68. This metal has a high stability in air. The salt of this element with a pink color has sharp adsorption spectra in infrared, visible and ultraviolet light. This malleable metal is applied in order to adding in alloys with other metals such as vanadium to decrease their hardness and increase the workability of them. On the other hand, it is applied to the glass composition of some goggles which used in some conditions such as welding due to its adsorption of infrared light. As other applications for erbium could also point to cases including used as a filter in photography, in optical fibers to amplify signals and finally because of its pink color, it is used as an enamel glaze colorant in porcelain and glass. Although the determination of erbium which present in

the human body is so difficult but it is recognized that there are highest levels of this metal in bones, whereas smaller amounts can find in the kidneys and liver. This metal is considered to be somewhat toxic^{36,37}.

At this paper a new erbium PVC membrane electrode based on lipophilic ionophore was prepared. In order to fabrication of this sensor the proper amount of 3-hydroxy-*N'*-(pyridine-2-ylmethylene)-2-naphthohydrazide (Fig. 1) was applied as an active material.

Fig. 1. 3-Hydroxy-*N'*-(pyridine-2-ylmethylene)-2-naphthohydrazide structure.

Experimental

Reagents :

All nitrate and chloride salts of several cations, the membrane materials such as high respective molecular weight PVC, tetrahydrofuran (THF), sodium tetra phenyl borate (NaTPB), and the reagent grades of nitrobenzene (NB), acetophenone (AP), benzyl acetate (BA), di butyl phthalate (DBP) with the highest purity, which were used with no additional amendment except for vacuum drying over P₂O₅, were procured from Merck and Aldrich. Moreover the electro active material 3-hydroxy-*N'*-(pyridine-2-ylmethylene)-2-naphthohydrazide was purchased from Fluka. It should be noted in all the experiments doubly distilled deionized water was applied.

EMF measurements :

The following system was employed to assemble the electrochemical cell in order to EMF measurements :

Ag-AgCl|internal solution, 1.0 × 10⁻³ M ErCl₃|PVC membrane|test solution|Hg-Hg₂Cl₂, KCl (satd.)

The electrochemical cell consists of two reference electrode, one Ag/AgCl electrode as an internal reference electrode and a saturated calomel electrode as a reference electrode which were purchased from Azar Electrode Co. (Iran) so that both electrodes were connected to a milli-

volt meter and the Er³⁺ PME was used as an indicator electrode³⁸.

PVC membrane electrode preparation :

In this present research the membrane was prepared by mixing the needed quantities of the membrane components such as 30 mg powdered PVC as a polymeric matrix, 2 mg 3-hydroxy-*N'*-(pyridine-2-ylmethylene)-2-naphthohydrazide as a lipophilic ionophore, 1 mg NaTPB as an anionic additive and 67 mg AP as a plasticizer in 3–5 mL THF as an inert solvent. In the next stage, the resulting mixture was carried over into a glass dishes and left to evaporate THF slowly until obtaining the oily concentration mixture. A transparent membrane of about 0.3 mm thickness was formed to a Pyrex tube (3–5 mm o.d. on top) by dipping and keeping into the oily mixture for about 5 s. After pulling out the tube from the mixture and keeping in the room temperature for at least 12 h, it was filled with internal filling solution (1.0 × 10⁻³ M ErCl₃) and immersing in the same solution for 24 h. In order to internal reference electrode a silver/silver chloride electrode was employed^{39–45}.

Results and discussion

Potential response of the electrode :

To evaluate the selectivity of the proposed electrode based on 3-hydroxy-*N'*-(pyridine-2-ylmethylene)-2-naphthohydrazide, a large number of different sensors for various types of cations were fabricated. Pursuant to the obtained results, the best response in a widish concentration with a slope of 21.3 ± 0.6 mV per decade pertains to erbium ion (Fig. 2). This has been attributed

Fig. 2. Potential responses of various ion selective electrodes based on 3-hydroxy-*N'*-(pyridine-2-ylmethylene)-2-naphthohydrazide.

Table 1. Composition of membrane ingredients

Electrode No.	Composition of membrane (wt.%)							Slope (mV/decade)	Dynamic linear range (M)
	PVC	NB	AP	BA	DBP	NaTPB	Ionophore		
1	30	66	–	–	–	2	2	10.5 ± 0.6	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁵ –1.0 × 10 ⁻²
2	30	–	66	–	–	2	2	13.4 ± 0.1	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁵ –1.0 × 10 ⁻²
3	30	–	–	66	–	2	2	33.1 ± 0.6	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁶ –1.0 × 10 ⁻²
4	30	–	–	–	66	2	2	25.0 ± 0.2	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁶ –1.0 × 10 ⁻²
5	30	–	68	–	–	0	2	14.3 ± 0.4	5.0 × 10 ⁻⁶ –1.0 × 10 ⁻²
6	30	–	67	–	–	1	2	21.3 ± 0.6	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁶ –1.0 × 10 ⁻²
7	30	–	65	–	–	3	2	24.5 ± 0.2	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁶ –1.0 × 10 ⁻²
8	30	–	68	–	–	1	1	17.1 ± 0.3	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁶ –1.0 × 10 ⁻²
9	30	–	66	–	–	1	3	27.7 ± 0.1	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁶ –1.0 × 10 ⁻²
10	30	–	66	–	–	1	4	33.4 ± 0.5	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁶ –1.0 × 10 ⁻²

to the specific interaction between the Er³⁺ and ionophore.

Effect of membrane composition :

Regarding to this fact that nature and amount of the membrane composition has a remarkable effect on the response of electrode, it was optimized for each component such as plasticizer, additive and ionophore respectively in order to acquire the best permanent, noiseless and repeatable potentials response^{46,47}. Due to the relevant results which is summarized in Table 1 using of acetophenone in presence of four other plasticizers leading to the better Nernstian behavior of sensor. In fact, the plasticizer leads to reclaim the performance of the sensor via enhancing the capability to move of the ionophore in the PVC membrane matrix. One other ingredient employing as an anionic additive in this type of sensors is NaTPB which enhance the performance of membrane electrode via simplification the proceeding of ion extraction into membrane by diminish the ohmic resistance which causes to incrementing the sensitivity of the electrode. Moreover the proper amounts of ionophore as an active material have the most influence on selectivity of membrane^{48,49}. As a result the best Nernstian potential response was illustrated by membrane's composition of 30% PVC, 2% ionophore, 1% NaTPB and 67% AP (electrode no. 6).

Calibration curve :

The optimized membrane electrode demonstrated Nernstian response in widish linear range of calibration

curve (1.0 × 10⁻⁶ to 1.0 × 10⁻² M) with slope equal 21.3 ± 0.6 mV per decade and detection limit of 7.0 × 10⁻⁷ M which was acquired from the intersection of the two extrapolated segments of the calibration graph. The potential response of Er³⁺ electrode versus concentration changes of primary ion, which is nominated as calibration curve, was illustrated in Fig. 3.

pH effect :

The pH range which the potential response of electrode is independent of concentration changes of H₃O⁺ ion was determined by employing 1.0 × 10⁻³ M of Er³⁺ solution over the pH 1.0–11.0. Pursuant to Fig. 4, which represents the effects of changes in hydrogen ion concentration on the potential response of electrode, the changes of potential at pH values lower than 3.1 are ascribed to

Fig. 3. Calibration curves of the 3-hydroxy-*N'*-(pyridine-2-ylmethylene)-2-naphthohydrazide based Er³⁺ sensor.

Fig. 4. The pH effect of the test solution on the potential response of the erbium sensor.

protonated ionophore in solution which leads to negligible sensitivity toward Er^{3+} ions and strong response to the H_3O^+ , while the changes of potential at pH values higher than 9.7 imputed to formation of some hydroxyl complexes of Er^{3+} ions in solution⁵⁰, and finally there was no considerable shifts on the potential response in pH range of 3.1–9.7.

Dynamic response time :

In order to evaluate the dynamic response time of electrode, the various concentration of erbium ions (1.0×10^{-6} to $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$) was applied from lower to higher concentration respectively. According to Fig. 5, which shows the dynamic time of the potential response of electrode versus the diverse concentration of erbium

Fig. 5. Dynamic response time of Er^{3+} sensor.

ions⁵¹, Er^{3+} electrode displayed a fairly quick response time about ~ 10 s.

Selectivity of the sensor :

Study on interference of other cations on the potential response of primary ion, which is done via the selectivity coefficients, is one of the most important specifications of ion selective electrode that is usually carried out by the matched potential method (MPM). According to this way, the matched potential method selectivity coefficient (K_{MPM}) was defined via the ratio of the primary ion (A) and the interfering ion (B) activity ($K_{\text{MPM}} = a_A/a_B$) by adding a certain amount of primary ion and various interfering ions solution during two separate testing to the same standard solution and measuring potential for interfering ion until matches with acquired potential for primary ion^{52–57}. According to Table 2, which shows the selectivity coefficients for different monovalent, divalent and trivalent cations, there was no superiority to selectivity of the membrane electrode toward interfering ions in comparison with erbium ion.

Table 2. Selectivity coefficients ($K_{\text{Er}^{3+}}^{\text{MPM}}$) of proposed Er^{3+} sensor

Interfering ion	$K_{\text{Er,B}}^{\text{MPM}}$	Interfering ion	$K_{\text{Er,B}}^{\text{MPM}}$
Pr^{3+}	8.0×10^{-4}	Dy^{3+}	6.5×10^{-4}
La^{3+}	8.5×10^{-4}	Yb^{3+}	8.0×10^{-4}
Tm^{3+}	3.0×10^{-3}	Pb^{2+}	4.0×10^{-3}
Lu^{3+}	6.0×10^{-3}	Na^+	1.0×10^{-5}
Eu^{3+}	7.0×10^{-4}	K^+	1.0×10^{-4}
Ho^{3+}	3.0×10^{-5}	Co^{2+}	5.0×10^{-4}
Gd^{3+}	5.5×10^{-4}	Ca^{2+}	2.5×10^{-4}
Sm^{3+}	2.8×10^{-4}	Fe^{3+}	5.8×10^{-3}
Nd^{3+}	7.0×10^{-4}	Cr^{3+}	2.5×10^{-3}
Tb^{3+}	5.7×10^{-4}	Ni^{2+}	5.5×10^{-3}

Analytical applications :

One way to assessment the performance of ion selective electrodes, is analytical applications such as potentiometric titration and recovery of primary ion in presence of other ions. In order to do potentiometric titration, 25 mL of $1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ Er}^{3+}$ solution was titrated by the specified amounts of $1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ EDTA whereas the erbium electrode was applied as an indicator electrode. According to Fig. 6, which exhibits the poten-

Fig. 6. Potential titration curves of 25 mL 1.0×10^{-4} mol L $^{-1}$ Er $^{3+}$ solution with 1.0×10^{-2} mol L $^{-1}$ of EDTA.

tial response of electrode versus adding diverse volume of EDTA solution, this Er $^{3+}$ electrode would be able to apply successfully as an indicator electrode to determine the amount of erbium ions in solution.

Conclusion

Using 3-hydroxy-*N'*-(pyridine-2-ylmethylene)-2-naphthohydrazide as a lipophilic ionophore show the acceptable sensitivity toward Er $^{3+}$ ion which was attributed to the specific interaction between the Er $^{3+}$ and this electro active material that was employed as a selector element to fabrication of a novel ion selective electrode based on polymeric liquid exchange membrane. Due to the results of various tests the best Nernstian response with the slope of 21.3 ± 0.6 mV per decade belongs to the membrane composition containing 2% ionophore, 1% NaTPB, 30% PVC, 67% AP over the wide concentration range of 1.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-2} mol L $^{-1}$ Er $^{3+}$ and a detection limit of 7.0×10^{-7} mol L $^{-1}$. Independent pH range, which found no significant change in potential response, was over the range of 3.1–9.7. In addition this electrode displayed a fast response time about 10 s. This sensor show the good sensitivity toward Er $^{3+}$ ion in presence of other interfering ion. Finally the proposed electrode played admissible role as an indicator electrode in order to do analytical applications.

References

1. A. Mazzucotelli, F. DePaz, E. Magi and R. Frache, *Anal. Sci.*, 1992, **8**, 189.
2. M. E. Meyerhoff and M. N. Opydche, *Adv. Clin. Chem.*, 1986, **25**, 1.

3. N. Shibata, N. Fudagawa and M. Kubota, *Anal. Chem.*, 1991, **63**, 636.
4. B. Li, Y. Sun and M. J. Yin, *Anal. At. Spectrom.*, 1999, **14**, 1843.
5. Y. M. Liu, *Spectrosc. Spect. Anal.*, 2004, **24**, 1257.
6. J. E. Sonke and V. J. M. Salters, *J. Anal. Atom. Spectrosc.*, 2004, **19**, 235.
7. G. J. Moody, B. B. Saad and J. D. R. Thomas, *Sel. Electrode Rev.*, 1988, **10**, 71.
8. H. A. Zamani, M. Masrounia, M. Rostame-Faroge, M. R. Ganjali and H. Behmadi, *Sensor Lett.*, 2008, **6**, 759.
9. H. A. Zamani, G. Rajabzadeh, M. Masrounia, A. Dejbord and M. R. Ganjali, *Desalination*, 2009, **249**, 560.
10. F. Faridbod, M. R. Ganjali, B. Larijani and P. Norouzi, *Mat. Sci. Eng. C-Mater.*, 2009, **29**, 2388.
11. H. A. Zamani, G. Rajabzadeh, A. Firouz and M. R. Ganjali, *J. Anal. Chem.*, 2007, **62**, 1080.
12. H. A. Zamani, M. R. Ganjali, P. Norouzi and M. Adib, *Sensor Lett.*, 2007, **5**, 522.
13. H. A. Zamani, M. T. Hamed-Mosavian, E. Aminzadeh, M. R. Ganjali, M. Ghaemy, H. Behmadi and F. Faridbod, *Desalination* 2010, **250**, 56.
14. K. Alizadeh, R. Parooi, P. Hashemi, B. Rezaei and M. R. Ganjali, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2011, **186**, 1794.
15. H. A. Zamani, M. T. Hamed-Mosavian, E. Hamidfar, M. R. Ganjali and P. Norouzi, *Mater. Sci. Eng. (C)*, 2008, **28**, 1551.
16. M. R. Abedi and H. A. Zamani, *Anal. Lett.*, 2008, **41**, 2251.
17. H. A. Zamani, M. R. Ganjali, P. Norouzi, A. Tajarodi and Y. Hanifehpour, *J. Chil. Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **52**, 1332.
18. H. A. Zamani, J. Abedini-Torghabeh and M. R. Ganjali, *Bull. Korean Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **27**, 835.
19. M. Hosseini, S. D. Abkenar, M. R. Ganjali and F. Faridbod, *Mat. Sci. Eng. C-Mater.*, 2011, **31**, 428.
20. H. A. Zamani, A. Imani, A. Arvinfar, F. Rahimi, M. R. Ganjali, F. Faridbod and S. Meghdadi, *Mater. Sci. Eng. (C)*, 2011, **31**, 588.
21. M. R. Abedi, H. A. Zamani, M. R. Ganjali and P. Norouzi, *Intern. J. Environ. Anal. Chem.*, 2008, **88**, 353.
22. H. A. Zamani, *Anal. Lett.*, 2008, **41**, 1850.
23. M. R. Ganjali, H. Shams, F. Faridbod, L. Hajiaghbababaei and P. Norouzi, *Mat. Sci. Eng. C-Bio. S.*, 2009, **29**, 1380.
24. H. A. Zamani, G. Rajabzadeh and M. R. Ganjali, *Sensor Lett.*, 2009, **7**, 114.
25. H. A. Zamani, M. Nekoei, M. Mohammadhosseini and M. R. Ganjali, *Mater. Sci. Eng. (C)*, 2010, **30**, 480.

26. H. A. Zamani, M. Mohammadhossieni, M. Nekoei and M. R. Ganjali, *Sensor Lett.*, 2010, **8**, 303.
27. M. R. Ganjali, P. Norouzi, A. Atrian, F. Faridbod, S. Meghdadi and M. Giahi, *Mat. Sci. Eng. C-Bio. S.*, 2009, **29**, 205.
28. H. A. Zamani, M. Rohani, A. Zangeneh-Asadabadi, M. S. Zabihi, M. R. Ganjali and M. Salavati-Niasari, *Mater. Sci. Eng. (C)*, 2010, **30**, 917.
29. M. R. Ganjali, S. O. Ranaei-Siadat, H. Rashedi, M. Rezapour and P. Norouzi, *Int. J. Electrochem. Sci.*, 2011, **6**, 3684.
30. H. A. Zamani, M. Masrournia, S. Sahebhasagh and M. R. Ganjali, *Anal. Lett.*, 2009, **42**, 555.
31. M. Mohammadhossieni, H. A. Zamani and M. Nekoei, *Anal. Lett.*, 2009, **42**, 298.
32. F. Joz-Yarmohammadi, H. A. Zamani and F. Mohammadabadi, *Int. J. Electrochem. Sci.*, 2015, **10**, 8124.
33. H. A. Zamani, G. Rajabzadeh, A. Firouz and A. A. Ariaii-Rad, *J. Braz. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **16**, 1061.
34. M. Nekoei, H. A. Zamani and M. Mohammadhossieni, *Anal. Lett.*, 2009, **42**, 284.
35. J. Emsley, "Nature's building blocks : an A-Z guide to the elements", Oxford University, 2003.
36. H. A. Zamani, *Anal. Lett.*, 2009, **42**, 615.
37. N. N. Greenwood and A. Earnshaw, "Chemistry of the Elements", Pergamon, New York, 1984.
38. H. A. Zamani, M. Masrournia, H. Mohamadzadeh, M. R. Ganjali, M. Rahimizadeh and P. Ziaei, *Mater. Sci. Eng. (C)*, 2009, **29**, 976.
39. H. A. Zamani, M. S. Zabihi, M. Rohani, A. Zangeneh-Asadabadi, M. R. Ganjali, F. Faridbod and S. Meghdadi, *Mater. Sci. Eng. (C)*, 2011, **31**, 409.
40. H. A. Zamani, M. R. Ganjali, H. Behmadi and M. A. Behnajady, *Mater. Sci. Eng. (C)*, 2009, **29**, 1535.
41. F. Mohammadabadi, H. A. Zamani, F. Joz-Yarmohammadi and M. R. Abedi, *Int. J. Electrochem. Sci.*, 2015, **10**, 2791.
42. H. A. Zamani, M. R. Ganjali, P. Norouzi and M. Adib, *Mater. Sci. Eng. (C)*, 2008, **28**, 157.
43. H. A. Zamani, M. R. Ganjali, F. Faridbod and M. Salavati-Niasari, *Mater. Sci. Eng. (C)*, 2012, **32**, 564.
44. H. A. Zamani, R. Kamjoo, M. Mohammadhossieni, M. Zaferoni, Z. Rafati, M. R. Ganjali, F. Faridbod and S. Meghdadi, *Mater. Sci. Eng. (C)*, 2012, **32**, 447.
45. H. A. Zamani, M. Mohammadhossieni, Saeed Haji-Mohammadrezazadeh, F. Faridbod, M. R. Ganjali, S. Meghdadi and A. Davoodnia, *Mater. Sci. Eng. (C)*, 2012, **32**, 712.
46. E. Ammann, E. Pretsch, W. Simon, E. Lindner, A. Bezegh and E. Pungor, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1985, **171**, 119.
47. M. Masrournia, H. A. Zamani, H. A. Mirrashid, M. R. Ganjali and F. Faridbod, *Mater. Sci. Eng. (C)*, 2011, **31**, 574.
48. H. A. Zamani, B. Feizyadeh, F. Faridbod and M. R. Ganjali, *Mater. Sci. Eng. (C)*, 2011, **31**, 1379.
49. E. Bakker, P. Bühlmann and E. Pretsch, *Chem. Rev.*, 1997, **97**, 3083.
50. H. A. Zamani, A. Arvinfar, F. Rahimi, A. Imani, M. R. Ganjali and S. Meghdadi, *Mater. Sci. Eng. (C)*, 2011, **31**, 307.
51. H. A. Zamani, F. Faridbod and M. R. Ganjali, *Mater. Sci. Eng. (C)*, 2013, **33**, 608.
52. A. Sil, V. S. Ijeri and A. K. Srivastava, *Sens. Actuators (B)*, 2005, **106**, 648.
53. H. A. Zamani, F. Naghavi-Reyabbi, F. Faridbod, M. Mohammadhosseini, M. R. Ganjali, A. Tadjarodi and M. Rad, *Mater. Sci. Eng. (C)*, 2013, **33**, 870.
54. H. A. Zamani, A. Zanganeh-Asadabadi, M. Rohani, M. S. Zabihi, J. Fadaee, M. R. Ganjali, F. Faridbod and S. Meghdadi, *Mater. Sci. Eng. (C)*, 2013, **33**, 984.
55. M. Ebrahimi, H. A. Zamani and M. R. Abedi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2014, **91**, 431.
56. H. A. Zamani, F. Faridbod and M. R. Ganjali, *Mater. Sci. Eng. (C)*, 2014, **33**, 488.
57. H. A. Zamani and F. Faridbod, *J. Anal. Chem.*, 2014, **69**, 1073.